

Studies on the Solubilization of *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of Phenyl Glyoxal Nitrile by Cationic Surfactants and Effect of Electrolytes on Micelle Formation

Wahid U. Malik and Ajay K. Jain

Studies on the solubilization of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal nitrile by cationic surfactants viz., cetyl pyridinium bromide, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide and dodecyl pyridinium bromide, were carried out. The amount of the anil solubilized was evaluated from light absorption measurements at 505 $m\mu$. The solubilization data also provided information about critical micelle concentration (c.m.c.) values. These values were found to be $6.6 \times 10^{-4}M$, $7.8 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $9 \times 10^{-3}M$ for cetyl pyridinium bromide, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide and dodecyl pyridinium bromide, respectively. The effect of LiCl, NaCl and KCl on the c.m.c. of cetyl pyridinium bromide was also investigated. The c.m.c. was lowered in the order LiCl > NaCl > KCl. The results have been interpreted in terms of water structure.

Surface active agents possess the property of dissolving water insoluble substances in their relatively dilute aqueous solutions. In the existing literature data are available on the solubilization of large number of water insoluble substances viz., orange OT¹, azobenzene², dimethyl phthalate³, aliphatic alcohols⁴, dimethyl amino azobenzene⁵ etc. The dissolution of anils, which are water insoluble, has not so far been attempted with the help of surfactants. As a typical example of this class of compounds, studies on the solubilization of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal nitrile by cationic surfactants viz., cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB), cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB) and dodecyl pyridinium bromide (DPB) were carried out. The solubilization data so obtained were further used to determine the critical micelle concentration (c.m.c.) values of these surfactants. The effect of LiCl, NaCl, KCl on the c.m.c. of CPB, determined by this method, was also investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : CPB and CTMAB were B.D.H. products and recrystallized from acetone. DPB was prepared by the method described by Adderson and Taylor⁶. Anil was prepared as described by Krohnke and Borner⁷.

1. J. W. McBain and A. A. Green, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1731.
2. G. S. Hartley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1968.
3. McBain and McHan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3838.
4. W. D. Harkins and H. Oppenheimer, *ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 808.
5. I. M. Kolthoff and W. Stricks, *J. Phys. and Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 915.
6. J. E. Adderson and H. Taylor, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1964, **19**, 495.
7. F. Krhonke and E. Borner, *Ber. dtsh. Chem. Ges.*, 1936, **69**, 2012.

Estimation of solubilized anil: Standard solutions of surfactants were made in doubly distilled water. Series of solutions of varying surfactant concentrations were taken in capped conical flasks, with sufficient amount of anil added to form a small amount of excess solid. The solutions were agitated in an electrically driven shaker at room temperature ($27 \pm 2^\circ$) till equilibrium was established. The excess anil was allowed to settle down and clear solutions were used to estimate colorimetrically the amount of anil solubilized. The absorbance of clear solutions was measured at 505μ (absorption maximum).

A calibration curve between absorbance and amount of anil solubilized was obtained by dissolving known amounts of the anil in $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ CPB. This calibration curve was employed to evaluate from absorbance measurements, the amount of anil solubilized in different concentrations of CPB, CTMAB and DPB.

In case of CPB, the solubilization of the anil in presence of LiCl, NaCl and KCl was similarly studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Curves A, B and C (Fig. 1) are the plots between the amount of anil solubilized and concentrations of CPB, CTMAB and DPB, respectively. It is evident from Fig. 1 that the solubility of the anil beyond certain concentration value increases rapidly with increase in concentration of the surfactants. Obviously, these breaks in the curves A, B, and C (Fig. 1) correspond to the c.m.c. values of these surfactants. The c.m.c. values so obtained are found to be $6.6 \times 10^{-4} M$, $7.8 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $9 \times 10^{-3} M$ for CPB, CTMAB and DPB, respectively. These c.m.c. values are in good agreement with those mentioned in the literature.^{6,8,9}

Effect of electrolyte on micelle formation: The solubilization data of anil in CPB in presence of LiCl, NaCl and KCl are given in Figs. 2-4. The c.m.c. values of CPB in presence of LiCl, NaCl and KCl calculated from breaks in Figs. 2-4 are given in the Table I.

FIG-1, Plots between the amt. of the anil solubilized and surfactant concn.

FIG-2, Plots between the amount of anil solubilized and CPB concn in presence of LiCl, A- $1 \times 10^{-2} M$, B- $3 \times 10^{-3} M$, C- $1 \times 10^{-2} M$, D- $3 \times 10^{-3} M$, E- $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.

8. G. S. Hartley, B. Collie and C. S. Samis, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 795.

9. W. D. Harkins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1428.

It is evident from Table 1 that LiCl, NaCl and KCl lower the c.m.c. of CPB to different extents. The chloride ions being oppositely charged will cause the lowering of c.m.c.^{2,10,11}. Since the lowering caused by chloride ions should be same for the three electrolytes, it follows that Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ ions also affect the c.m.c. of the surfactant. This standpoint is in contradiction to that of Corrin and Harkins¹⁰.

FIG-3, Plots between the amount of anil solubilized and CPB concn. in presence of NaCl; A- 1×10^{-3} M, B- 3×10^{-3} M, C- 1×10^{-2} M, D- 3×10^{-2} M, E- 1×10^{-1} M.

FIG-4, Plots between the amount of anil solubilized and CPB concn. in presence of KCl; A- 1×10^{-3} M, B- 3×10^{-3} M, C- 1×10^{-2} M, D- 3×10^{-2} M, E- 1×10^{-1} M.

TABLE 1

Effect of LiCl, NaCl and KCl on the c.m.c. of CPB.

Electrolyte	Conc. of electrolyte (M)	c.m.c. of CPB ($\times 10^{-4}$ M)
	.0	6.6
	1×10^{-3}	3.7
	3×10^{-3}	2.7
LiCl	1×10^{-2}	2.1
	3×10^{-2}	1.3
	1×10^{-1}	1.1
	1×10^{-3}	4.5
	3×10^{-3}	3.5
NaCl	1×10^{-2}	2.4
	3×10^{-2}	1.6
	1×10^{-1}	1.4
	1×10^{-3}	5.2
	3×10^{-3}	4.0
KCl	1×10^{-2}	2.8
	3×10^{-2}	2.0
	1×10^{-1}	1.6

10. M. L. Corrin and W. D. Harkins, *Ibid.*, 1947, **69**, 679; 1947, **69**, 683.

11. H. B. Klevens, *J. Phys. and Colloid Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 1012.

The specific contribution of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ ions in affecting the c.m.c. of CPB may be interpreted in terms of water structure. Recent investigations¹²⁻¹⁶ have indicated that micelle formation in aqueous solution is primarily an entropy directed process in which enthalpy changes play minor role. The current hypothesis^{13,14} for micelle formation is based on "ice-berg" picture of water structure¹⁷. According to Frank and Evans¹⁷, water molecules become more ordered around the non-polar solute, with an increasing extent of hydrogen bonding in this region. Thus, in case of aqueous solutions of the surfactants, the hydrocarbon chains of the detergent ions are surrounded by a water structure (so called "ice-berg structure"). These "ice-berg structures" so induced by non-polar hydrocarbon chains represent a comparatively low entropy and energy state. Therefore, the transfer of the singly dispersed surfactant molecules into aggregated forms will bring about the disappearance of "ice-berg" structures around them and consequently gain in entropy will take place. Thus the presence of "ice-berg" structures around non-polar detergent ions is the cause of primary driving force for aggregation which is an entropy effect. Therefore, the more ordered the "ice-berg" structure around detergent ions, the greater will be the driving force for aggregation. It is anticipated, therefore, that structure promoting substances should enhance the tendency of micellization and consequently decrease the c.m.c. of the surfactants. On the other hand substances that break up the "ice-berg" water structure around detergent ions should retard the tendency of micellization and consequently increase the c.m.c.

The above arguments find strong support from the experimental observations that urea which breaks¹⁸ the water structure, is found to increase the c.m.c. values of surfactants¹⁹⁻²¹ appreciably.

It is well known^{17,22} that ions either promote or break water structure. Li^+ ion has structure promoting influence, and Na^+ and K^+ ions have structure breaking influence in the order $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$. In the light of above discussion, Li^+ ion as a structure promoter should cause the decrease in c.m.c., and Na^+ and K^+ as structure breakers should cause an increase in c.m.c. in the order $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$. Over and above the specific contributions of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ ions in affecting the c.m.c., the large lowering effect of chloride ions is superimposed. Since both chloride and Li^+ ions decrease the c.m.c., LiCl will decrease the c.m.c. most, NaCl will decrease less (since Na^+ ion increases the c.m.c.) and KCl will decrease still less (because K^+ ion increases the c.m.c. more in comparison to Na^+ ion). Therefore, it follows that these electrolytes should lower the c.m.c. in the order $\text{LiCl} > \text{NaCl} > \text{KCl}$. This is what has been experimentally observed.

Department of Chemistry,
University of Roorkee,
Roorkee.

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12. G. Stainsby and A. E. Alaxander, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **46**, 587.
13. E. D. Goddard and G. C. Benson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1957, **35**, 986.
14. E. D. Goddard, C. A. J. Hoeve and G. C. Benson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 593.
15. P. White and G. C. Benson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 1025.
16. B. D. Flockhart, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1961, **16**, 484.
17. H. S. Frank and M. W. Evans, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.
18. J. A. Rupley, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 2002.
19. W. Bruning and A. Holtzer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4865.
20. Wahid U. Malik and A. K. Jain, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1967, **14**, 37.
21. P. Mukherjee and A. Ray, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 190.
22. H. S. Frank and W. Y. Wen, *Discussion Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 133.